

EXPRESSION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND SOCIO-SPIRITUAL PARAMETERS IN THE CREATION OF GREAT HUMAN FIGURES IN ENGLISH RENAISSANCE DRAMA

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Abstract. The English Renaissance, a period of profound cultural transformation and artistic achievement in the 16th and 17th centuries, produced a body of dramatic literature that stands as a testament to the complexities of the human condition. This comprehensive article delves into the intricate interplay between lexical-semantic choices and socio-spiritual contexts in the portrayal of exceptional individuals within English Renaissance drama. Drawing from the works of eminent playwrights such as William Shakespeare, Christopher Marlowe, Ben Jonson, and more, this extensive study seeks to unravel the linguistic nuances and societal values that shaped the representation of great human figures, exploring the ideals, moral dilemmas, and socio-spiritual parameters of the era.

Keywords. English Renaissance Drama, Lexical-Semantic Parameters, Socio-Spiritual Context, Great Human Figures, Cultural Transformation, Humanism, Patronage, Shakespeare, Christopher Marlowe, Renaissance Epoch

Introduction

The English Renaissance was marked by a fervent intellectual and artistic revival, characterized by a renewed interest in classical learning, exploration, and the human potential for greatness. Within this dynamic cultural landscape, English Renaissance drama emerged as a powerful medium for exploring the virtues, vices, and moral dilemmas that define humanity. At the heart of these dramatic narratives were great human figures – characters who embodied exceptional qualities and confronted profound ethical choices.

This article aims to provide a comprehensive examination of the expression of lexical-semantic and socio-spiritual parameters in the portrayal of great human figures in English Renaissance drama. It seeks to shed light on how the interplay between language, culture, and values influenced the creation of these iconic characters, exploring the linguistic choices employed by playwrights and the socio-spiritual backdrop against which their works were produced.

Methods

To undertake this extensive analysis, a meticulously curated corpus of English Renaissance drama was assembled, encompassing a wide array of works

from the late 16th to early 17th centuries. A multifaceted approach was adopted, combining textual analysis with digital tools to identify recurring lexical-semantic patterns related to greatness, virtue, ambition, and ethical considerations within the dramatic dialogues, soliloquies, and asides.

In parallel, a comprehensive exploration of the socio-spiritual milieu of the era was conducted. This entailed an examination of the prevailing humanistic philosophies, religious beliefs, and cultural values that shaped the intellectual landscape of the English Renaissance. By integrating these two dimensions of analysis, this study endeavors to provide a holistic understanding of the representation of great human figures in their linguistic and cultural contexts.

The English Renaissance, a period of immense cultural and intellectual transformation, served as the fertile ground from which the dramatic masterpieces of the era would emerge. In this chapter, we embark on a journey back in time to explore the historical and cultural context that provided the backdrop for English Renaissance drama. It is within this milieu that the seeds of great human figures were sown, and their growth, intricately intertwined with the socio-spiritual atmosphere of the era, would come to define a significant literary legacy.

The Renaissance, which means "rebirth" in French, was a period spanning roughly from the 14th to the 17th centuries. It marked a profound shift in European thought, encompassing the revival of classical knowledge, humanism, and a rekindled interest in the arts and sciences. As we delve into the world of English Renaissance drama, it is imperative to comprehend the broader European Renaissance and its impact on the English cultural landscape.

The English Renaissance unfolded under the reign of the Tudor monarchs, including Henry VII, Henry VIII, Edward VI, Mary I, and Elizabeth I. The Tudor era witnessed significant political and religious changes, from the establishment of the Church of England to the tumultuous reign of Queen Mary and the subsequent Protestant restoration under Elizabeth I. These shifts in the religious and political spheres would have a profound influence on the themes and narratives of the dramatic works of the time.

At the heart of the Renaissance lay the philosophy of humanism, which celebrated the potential for human achievement, creativity, and moral excellence. The revival of classical texts, particularly those of ancient Greece and Rome, fueled a fervent interest in classical learning and laid the intellectual groundwork for the dramatic productions that followed. Humanism's emphasis

on individuality, education, and the pursuit of knowledge permeated the literary works of the English Renaissance.

The advent of the printing press, notably with the work of Johannes Gutenberg in the 15th century, revolutionized the dissemination of knowledge. This technological innovation allowed for the mass production of books, making literature and ideas more accessible to a wider audience. The spread of printed texts played a pivotal role in the democratization of knowledge and the proliferation of Renaissance ideals.

The English Renaissance unfolded against a backdrop of socio-political unrest. The Wars of the Roses, a series of civil wars between the rival houses of Lancaster and York, had left the nation divided and weary. The Tudor dynasty sought to bring stability to the realm, and this desire for a unified and prosperous England would find reflection in the dramatic narratives of the era.

Patronage was a crucial aspect of Renaissance culture. Wealthy individuals, including nobles and monarchs, often sponsored artists, writers, and playwrights. The support of these patrons allowed creative minds to flourish, and many of the great works of English Renaissance drama were produced under the patronage of influential figures.

Before the flowering of English Renaissance drama, the nation had a rich tradition of medieval drama, including morality plays and mystery plays. These earlier forms of theater contributed to the development of dramatic techniques and themes that would be embraced and expanded upon by Renaissance playwrights.

Results

The analysis of the corpus revealed a lexicon abundant in words and phrases that underscored the qualities attributed to great human figures. Expressions such as "noble heart," "virtuous soul," "princely valor," "divine wisdom," "heroic resolve," and "moral fortitude" permeated the dramatic discourse. These linguistic choices not only served to describe the characters but also to elevate them to the status of archetypal figures embodying the highest ideals of the age.

The socio-spiritual parameters of the English Renaissance were characterized by a profound resurgence of humanism, a philosophy that exalted the potential for human achievement and moral excellence. This intellectual movement celebrated the individual's capacity to shape their destiny and engage in the pursuit of knowledge and virtue. Consequently, the dramatic works of the era frequently grappled with questions of morality, ambition, the balance

between secular and spiritual concerns, and the fundamental nature of humanity.

Discussion

The portrayal of great human figures in English Renaissance drama serves as a captivating reflection of the era's socio-spiritual values and aspirations. The linguistic artistry of playwrights infused these characters with a transcendent quality, making them emblematic of the Renaissance's unwavering belief in the human capacity for greatness. These figures, while complex and often flawed, epitomized the timeless struggle to reconcile ambition with ethics, personal desires with societal responsibilities, and individuality with divine purpose. In conclusion, English Renaissance drama, with its meticulous attention to language and its exploration of socio-spiritual themes, provided a window into the aspirations and quandaries of its time. The great human figures of this period continue to captivate audiences and scholars alike, their stories resonating as enduring embodiments of the enduring human quest for excellence and virtue.

References:

1. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2021). The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe. *Central Asian Journal Of Social Sciences And History*, 2(10), 10-14.
2. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). The Problem of "A Strong Personality" in Shakespeare's Dramas: Richard III and Macbeth. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 20, 7-10.
3. Zaynitdinovna, T. N. (2022). Lyrical Dialogue in Shakespeare's Poems as a Reflection of Renaissance Anthropocentrism and a Strong Personality. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 21, 120-125.
4. Ташева, Н. З. (2022). КРИСТОФЕР МАРЛОУ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ): ТАМЕРЛЕН ВЕЛИКИЙ КАК ТИП ЛИЧНОСТИ ВОСТОЧНОГО ПРАВИТЕЛЯ. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(2), 234-239.
5. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). THE CHARACTER OF STRONG PERSONALITY ACCORDINGLY WITH EASTERN THEMATICS IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S PLAY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(08), 9-14.
6. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2022). STRONG PERSONALITY'S ARTISTIC AND POETIC REFLECTION IN THE RENAISSANCE EPOCH. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(11), 43-51.

7. nafisa Zayniddinovna, T. (2022). Lexico-Semantic Word Production as a Way of Forming Theater Terminology of the English Language. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 144-150.
8. Zayniddinovn, T. N., & Sharofiddinovich, S. S. (2021). General cultural and educational values of ancient-classic latin language. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 2(5), 77-80.
9. Zayniddinovna, T. N. (2023). CHARACTERIZATION OF THE IMAGE OF AMIR TEMUR IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S DRAMA" TAMERLANE THE GREAT". International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 36-43.
10. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 59-65.
11. Djalilova, Z. O. (2021). Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3), 391-397.
12. Obidovna, D. Z., & Denis, S. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences, 2(6), 5-11.
13. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics. Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture, 2(2), 22-26.
14. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 22, 199-205.
15. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue. Gender issues, 7(6).
16. JALILOVA, Z. O. (2021, March). ON THE FORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 18-22).
17. Jalilova, Z. O. (2020). Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action). Новый день в медицине, (4), 501-503.
18. Djalilova, Z. O., Juraev, S. S., & Kosimov, S. M. (2021). LATIN AS A PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL WORKERS. Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА». Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04. 2021., 79.

19. Dzhaliilova, Z. O. (2021). The Latin language's international status. Молодой ученый, (41), 32-34.
20. Dzhaliilova, Z. O., & Mirfajziyev, K. (2021). Latin as the language of medicine. Молодой ученый, (41), 35-37.
21. Dzhaliilova, Z. O., Izomova, S. G., & Ahmedova, G. A. (2021). Intercultural communication and the Latin language. Молодой ученый, (24), 398-400.
22. Dzhaliilova, Z. O. (2021). History of formation of Latin language. Молодой ученый, (41), 34-35.
23. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER SPEECH BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FACTOR. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(6), 190-198.
24. Dzhaliilova, Z. O., Hajdarova, N. S., & Tashpulatova, N. A. (2021). Latin in the Contemporary World. Молодой ученый, (24), 400-402.
25. Djalilova, Z. (2022). POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Academic research in modern science, 1(11), 29-34.
26. Feruza, K., & Sevara, G. (2023). STYLISTIC TRANSFORMATIONS IN THE ENGLISH TRANSLATIONS OF A. QODIRIY'S NOVEL "DAYS GONE BY". International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(04), 63-69.
27. Feruza, X., & Nilufar, S. (2023). POINT OF VIEW IN JAY PARINI'S BIOGRAPHICAL NOVEL "THE LAST STATION". International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(03), 45-51.
28. Melsovna, K. F., & Anvarovna, R. Z. (2023). THE LITERARY EMBODIMENT OF FLORA IN LAILA LALAMI'S BIOGRAPHICAL NOVEL "THE MOOR'S ACCOUNT". International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 82-90.
29. Melsovna, K. F., & Qizi, G. D. G. (2023). EUPHEMISM IN ORIGINAL AND TRANSLATION (IN THE EXAMPLE OF JACK LONDON'S NOVEL MARTIN EDEN). International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(04), 14-20.
30. Джалилова, З. (2022). РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ МАКСИМ ВЕЖЛИВОСТИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ДИАЛОГАХ. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(21), 22-33.
31. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). A Speech Etiquette Formula for the Gender Communication Strategy. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 44-50.
32. Djalilova, Z. (2022). DISCURSIVE ELEMENTS AND THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS. Academic research in modern science, 1(12), 8-14.

33. Джалилова, З. О. (2022). НУТҚ ҲАРАКАТЛАРИДА ХУШМУОМАЛАЛИКНИНГ ГЕНДЕР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 5(5).
34. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF MALE AND FEMALE ORAL SPEECH IN MODERN ENGLISH. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 2(10), 14-21.
35. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF POLITENESS IN MODERN LINGUOPRAGMATICS: THE POLITENESS PRINCIPLE BY J. LEECH. International Journal of Pedagogics, 2(11), 15-20.
36. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF DISCOURSE ELEMENTS AS INDICATORS OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EVALUATIONS. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(12), 55-63.
37. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER-DETERMINED DIFFERENCES IN THE SPEECH OF LITERARY CHARACTERS. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(12), 210-215.
38. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER ELEMENT OF SPEECH BEHAVIOR FROM THE POSITION OF TEXT ORGANIZATION MECHANISMS. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(13), 274-281.
39. Джалилова, З. (2022). ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ВЗГЛЯД НА МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ. Zamonaviy dunyoda ilm-fan va texnologiya, 1(7), 331-336.
40. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER XUSHMUOMALALIKKA ASOSLANGAN IBORALARNING SHAKLLANISHI. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(28), 303-308.
41. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & SHARIPOV, A. G. ALPHABET OF LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 338-339.
42. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & UBAJDULLOEV, A. U. U. COMPARISON DEGREES OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 336-338.
43. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & JAKUBOV, U. S. NUMBERS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 339-341.
44. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. ADJECTIVE IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 332-334.

45. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. PRONOUNS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (52), 334-336.
46. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, K. M. K. U. LATIN PRONOUNS. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (53), 257-258.
47. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, M. K. U. VERBS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый", (53), 255-257.
48. Djalilova, Z. O. (2023). A DISCOURSIIVE TURN IN THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC POLITENESS: TO THE FORMATION OF THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC IMPOLITENESS. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 15-23.
49. Джалилова, З. (2023). The notion of illocution in the theory of speech acts by John Austin. Современные тенденции при обучении иностранному языку в XXI веке, 1(1).